

INVESTIGATION OF A NEW OUT OF AUTOCLAVE PREPREG PLACEMENT PROCESS, MOULD CONCEPTS/RELEASE STRATEGIES AND REUSABLE HEATED BAGGING MATERIAL

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Abstract

Carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) parts provide advantages for light weight structures in aeronautical applications. However, state of the art manufacturing methods are too slow to meet the quantities needed for future aircraft demands. This paper focuses on a manufacturing process to improve overall cycle time from cutting the prepreg material to finishing the cured part. The process is based on a new tape laying process, which is capable to process 300 mm wide, unidirectional prepreg tapes, directly into the final three-dimensional part geometry. This is possible due to active in plane shearing of the tapes, which compensates length differences while placing it onto double curved surfaces. A heated mould ensures the needed tack to properly attach the prepreg tapes on the mould or other prepreg material. This mould is equipped with a new heating concept allowing heating rates of above 10 K/min. To avoid transfer issues with the shaped prepreg material the mould is also used for curing.

The process is designed to use out of autoclave prepreg material, allowing to cure with a consolidation pressure of only about 1 bar. Combinations of permanent (mould surface) and semi-permanent (release agents) release strategies are investigated. Release agent application methods and the amount of possible demoulding steps without recoating are tested to determine the most suited solution for a minimum mould preparation time. Finally, reusable bagging material with integrated heating elements is investigated. This research is part of the EFFICOMP project, funded by Horizon 2020.

Keywords tape placement; out of autoclave prepreg; release strategy; reusable bagging material.

1. Introduction

Today's demand by the mobility sector to reach any place in the world is higher than ever. To satisfy this need, about 20,500 (Airbus, 2017) to 22,510 (Boeing, 2016) aircrafts with a capacity of 100 seats and above as well as freighter aircrafts already exist today. According to the estimation of Airbus and Boeing the amount of aircrafts needed to satisfy future demands is even bigger. Airbus expects a total amount of 34,900 deliveries for the next 20 years (Airbus, 2017) whereas Boeing estimates a total amount of about 39,600 aircrafts (Boeing, 2016). In 2016 Airbus was not able to deliver the number of aircrafts demanded by the market. The company had net orders of 731 aircrafts of which only 688 could be delivered (Airbus, 2016). This means that current production methods hardly meet production cycle time requirements. This is the reason new efficient production processes are required in the future.

For the composite sector and state of the art manufacturing processes several major time-consuming sub processes for manufacturing CFRP-parts exist:

- *Part forming*: The process to shape the fabrics from 2D into the part geometry. Current processes are manual or automated with poor processing rates (kg/min).
- *Curing*: Heating the impregnated fibre geometry to a defined temperature is mostly done within an autoclave. This results in slow heating rates with high energy consumption.
- *Mould preparation for the preforming process*: Today mould cleaning and coating with release agent is mostly a manual and time-consuming process.
- *Mould preparation for the curing process*: The application of the vacuum bag and other needed consumables for the curing process are mostly time-consuming manual cutting and application steps of several onetime use materials.

Within the EU-Project EFFICOMP the Institute of Aircraft design of the University of Stuttgart addresses those issues with a new automated tape placement process and corresponding boundary conditions to minimize the effect of the other points.

2. Advanced Ply Placement Process (APP)

State of the art automated tape placements processes depend on relatively small tape widths. Small tape widths lead to many abutting edges. Therefore, the required tape width tolerances, for avoiding defects, are very demanding. Placing a tape over a double curved surface requires different lengths of the filaments within the tape. If the tape is wide and the part geometry too complex, wrinkles and buckling are hard to avoid. A certain temperature for controlling the tack of the prepreg tape is needed to ensure that the tape sticks to the mould. Inhomogeneous impregnation or temperature deviations can lead to debonding and tape slipping. Hence, process control methods of state of the art tape placement processes are complex and fault-prone.

The APP process, examined in this paper, avoids those problems due to a new forming approach: It allows the tapes to shear longitudinally and therefore permits to drape wide tapes over double curved surfaces.

Fig. 1. APP functionality

One key element is that this APP process uses gripper units, which consist of several clamping fingers. Each of those clamping fingers can move independently and thereby applies a defined pretension onto its tape segment. Hereby it is possible to shear the tape to compensate length differences within it (Fig. 1 (b)). The compaction roller is used to apply a defined pressure to ensure that occurring forces do not detach the tape from the mould during the shearing process (Fig. 1 (a)). The compaction roller is designed to adapt to the mould geometry and to apply a constant pressure over the whole contact surface on the tape, as shown in Fig. 1 (c). Roller compaction pressure also achieves part consolidation.

Fig. 2. Scheme of APP production cell (Szczesny *et al.*, 2016) and placement cycle

The APP production cell consists of two gripper robots on linear axes, a stationary roller robot, a heated mould on a rotary axis and a tape cutting and pickup station. The cutting and pickup station can be adapted to different ply tape lengths (Fig. 2 (a)). During production both gripper robots move to the pickup station and grab the tape. While they move to the placement position the mould rotates to a certain angle which corresponds to the fibre orientation required (Fig. 2 (b)). After that, the roller robot applies a force on the tape which leads to a pretension and pushes it down onto the mould (Fig. 2 (c)). At that point one gripper robot relaxes the tape while the roller robot drapes the tape towards the other gripper robot (Fig. 2 (d)). Then the roller robot moves back to its first touchdown position and the same procedure is executed on the second half of the tape (Fig. 2 (e)). This process is repeated until the part is completed.

3. APP from CAD to part

Understanding the draping process and the material behaviour is necessary to manufacture parts on a high automation level. Therefore, software tools are required which translate the CAD information to actual robot machine code. Fig. 3 shows the connection between material characterisation (a), CAD & ply-book (b), robot programming tool (c) and the final APP process (d).

Fig. 3. APP process chain, from CAD to part

For each unknown prepreg material a material behaviour data set must be generated. The data base contains shear, gliding and friction behaviour as a function of the gripper and roller forces, temperature and tape length. The placement positioning tool uses this material data base as well as kinematic and geometrical coherences to generate the tape placement trajectories.

For each discrete point on the tape trajectory one point for each gripper unit trajectory is calculated. According to the ply book, layers are defined and tape placement trajectories are generated automatically. This results in three point-to-point position vectors (including movement speed) as well as corresponding gripper or roller forces. The next step is to transfer those vectors to the robot programming tool (Fig. 3 (c)). It allows to simulate robot movements during the placement process. Furthermore, manual modifications of gripper or roller

position points, movement speed and forces are possible. Besides, it generates the machine code for the manufacturing robots.

3.1. Material data base

The main forming mechanism which enables the APP process to drape the 100-300 mm wide unidirectional prepreg tapes over double curved surfaces is shear-gliding between fibre filaments. The APP-process can control tape tension, roller compaction pressure and the gripper positions relative to the roller position. The adjustment of those parameters determines the efficiency of wrinkle removal in the unplaced tape. To achieve a proper tape position and consolidation, no wrinkles or other defects are allowed within the tape. This means that roller movement speed and thereby placement speed is limited by the time needed to compensate length differences in the tape before the roller has contact and pushes it onto the mould. One possibility to implement this is to use a database which links length differences in the tape with free tape lengths between gripper and roller units and tape tension.

The maximum tape tension is defined by the point below which no gliding between mould, tape and roller is occurring. This point is characterized by the mould and roller surfaces as well as the tape temperature and tension. It is important to notice that only tape temperature and tension are controllable variables.

A test rig was designed to describe the shear-gliding behaviour and the characteristic gliding point (Fig. 4 (a)). It consists of two sledges on a linear axis, an APP gripper unit and a tape clamping device which represents the compaction roller. One sledge contains a load cell and is attached to a spindle drive. The other sledge carries the gripper unit and is connected to the load cell sledge. The clamping device is fixed on a base plate and is operated by an actuator and controlled using the data of a load cell.

Fig. 4. Shear-gliding and friction testing rig

For examining the shear-gliding behaviour the prepreg tape is loaded according to Fig. 4 (b). The tape is clamped in the clamping device with a defined angle relative to the testing direction. This angle determines the length differences which must be compensated. After that, the other end of the tape is positioned in the gripper unit. During material characterization, the sledge moves to a position where all clamping fingers are extended half way and the gripper unit applies a certain tape tension. From here on, length differences are gradually compensated and load as well as position data are logged over time.

In a second testing step the critical friction point (the transition from static to a gliding state) is characterized. Therefore, tape tension is linearly increased by augmenting the pneumatic pressure of the clamping fingers. Clamping finger pressure, loading and the gripper position are logged over time.

The result of the tests will be a material data base which holds the needed and maximal allowed finger gripper force as well as the needed roller pressure for all possible length differences within the tape and needed time to compensate them. The finger gripper design allows a maximal length compensation of 100 mm. Data points are stored with 10 mm deltas. Test series will be executed for 25°C, 30°C and 35°C ambient temperature and tape lengths of 0.5 m, 1 m and 1.5 m.

3.2. Placement positioning tool

Due to the nearly infinite possibilities to place the tapes on the mould a placement positioning tool is developed which defines the optimal placement sequence as well as the robots' movements. The tape deformation, which is necessary to predict the tapes' paths, is calculated by a kinematic approach. A finite-element based approach has also been considered but was found too calculation intensive for optimization loops.

The kinematic draping approach is based on the assumptions that the tape only deforms by in-plane shearing as well as out-of-plane bending. It is also assumed that the width of the tape does not change by shear deformation. Due to the absence of weft yarns and stitching threads the material's behaviour meets the assumptions very well. The tapes are equally discretized in length and width direction to minimize the deviation. Fig. 5 (a) shows the part geometry with the predicted first tape position.

Fig. 5. Part geometry with calculated tape position and roller, gripper placement orientation

In a first loop, the program defines a starting line on the tool surface. This line has a constant angle and represents the middle of the first tape. Based on this, the tape's edges are calculated using the kinematic approach described above. Relating to the edges of the previous tape, the path of the neighbouring tape is calculated. This procedure is repeated until the whole tool surface is covered. With the presence of double-curved surfaces the tapes will change their direction due to draping effects. These effects are minimized by an optimization loop which finds the optimal position of the starting tape. In this loop, a whole set of lay-ups using different starting lines is calculated. The minimum fibre angle deviation is used as criterion to select the best lay-up suited – under the condition that a defined maximum local shear angle is not reached.

Based on the resulting lay-up of one layer, the robots' movements are calculated for every tape. The starting position of the roller robot is chosen in the way that the maximum shearing angle is equal at both ends of the tape.

The positions and orientations of the gripper units and the press roller are calculated considering the flowing criteria (Fig. 5 (b)): While the press roller moves towards the tensioned tape, following the calculated placement trajectory, it is aligned orthogonal to the mould surface. The gripper robot is moving in a plane which is perpendicular to the mould surface and tangential to the roller – mould contact line. The angle between tape and mould surface is as small as possible without touching the mould at another point. Orientation deviations may occur due to collision prevention.

The robots' velocities, the normal force of the roll and the tape's tension are extracted and interpolated from an empirical database which is based on the shearing angle and the shear rate.

The data output of the placement positioning tool will be three trajectories for the roller and the two gripper units. Each trajectory includes position points, tool orientation, movement speed to the next point and gripper finger tension or roller pressure.

3.3. Robot programming tool

The Robot programming tool is a commercial software for programming and simulating robot movements. It is fed with the data from the placement positioning tool and transforms it into machine code. During the simulation of the robot movements it is possible to manipulate trajectory data. This is also possible during the physical process itself. When connected to the APP-cell, the software represents the positions and orientations of the physical robots. This allows to manipulate any tape placement trajectory, to feed the data back into the placement positioning tool and to recalculate each unplaced trajectory.

3.4. Part manufacturing

A comprehensive approach considering all manufacturing sub-processes, from the fibre and resin material to the cured part, is needed to minimize CFRP - part production cycle times. Fig. 6 describes the APP-process, representing a serial production cycle. Sub-processes per part (SP.P) are necessary for every part manufactured, while sub-processes per shift (SP.S) are repeated only once per shift. Several parts are manufactured per shift. Horizontal processes are sequential, vertical processes are parallel.

Sub-processes per shift (SP.S)						
Sub-processes per part (SP.P)						
SP.S.1: Mould preparation – full cleaning	SP.S.2: Mould preparation – application of release agent	SP.P.1: Mould preparation – basic cleaning	SP.P.2: Ply cutting	SP.P.4: Mould preparation – vacuum bagging	SP.P.5: Part curing	SP.P.5: Part demoulding
			SP.P.3: Part forming - APP			
SP.P.6: Part trimming						SP.S.3: Cleaning of gripper-, roller units and ply cutting/pick up station

Fig. 6. APP sub-processes

The goal of this study is to define an automated process which considers all sub-processes to fit into repeated 8 h shifts whilst producing as many parts as possible. The actual part cycle time is a function of many factors which can be summarized under part-, material-, and process related properties.

Characteristics such as the part geometry, the ply-book as well as the OoA prepreg material properties are mainly set according to the requirement specifications of the part. They have an influence on the ply cutting (SP.P.2), part forming (SP.P.3) and part trimming (SP.P.6) sub processes. Material behaviour is qualified (Fig. 4) and a realistic process chain including simulation and planning tools are established (Fig. 3) to minimize the cycle time.

Preparing process steps such as mould cleaning, application of release agent and consumables like vacuum bagging often are slow and manual processes. Improving their cycle time is most effective if they are simplified or even dispensed with for individual manufacturing cycles. For example, after demoulding a part a full cleaning step using chemical cleaning agents might not necessarily be needed. Only residuals contaminating the mould forming surface and air-evacuation lines must be cleaned to manufacture the next part. If it is possible to achieve this with a basic cleaning step, using weak mechanical removal methods (wipe cloth, air gun ...) only, recoating with release agent might be unnecessary. Possible combinations of permanent and semi-permanent release agents as well as reusable vacuum bagging material are investigated to determine possible process sequences where not all sub processes are needed for each manufacturing cycle. New heating concepts are studied to reduce the part cure time.

3.4.1. Mould concept for high heating rates

Long cure cycles of conventional autoclaves are another major time-consuming factor for manufacturing CFRP-parts. Poor heating rates due to the limitation to convection based heat transfer combined with a relatively high part and mould mass are the main reason for this. Typical autoclave heating rates are up to 2 K/min (Witik, 2012).

High heating rates and short dwell times at cure- or any potential hold temperatures are necessary for fast curing process. Dwell times are used for air transport within the laminate and for polymerisation of the resin.

Certain temperature slots, depending on the resin properties, are needed for minimizing the dwell time. Deviations towards lower temperatures lead to subpar air transportation and slower cure kinetics. Temperature deviations towards higher temperatures lead to reduced mechanical properties since the air transport slot is interrupted early and very high exothermal reactions may occur.

A new tool concept has been developed which targets these issues and shows a way to ensure fast heating rates and a homogeneous temperature distribution. It combines a relatively homogeneous heating wire patch with a low thermal mass and high insulation towards the environment. The meandering pattern (Fig. 7 (a)) of the heating patch is covered by a 0.3 mm thick glass fibre epoxy layer (Fig. 7 (b)). It serves as electrical insulation between part and mould.

Fig. 7 EFFICOMP - cure tool concept

A 15 mm thick sandwich core is located under the heating patch. It is thermoformable and its porous structure is partly filled with epoxy matrix. The core serves as thermal insulation and increases the mould stiffness. The back of the mould consists of a 10 mm thick glass fibre epoxy composite. It provides the stiffness necessary for shape retention during the cure cycle. Three temperature sensors are embedded in the laminate for temperature control. They are located about 3.5 mm below the mould surface on the diagonal of the mould ((Fig. 7 (a)).

The current configuration allows a maximum cure temperature of 165°C, heating rates between 15-20 K/min with an installed heating power of 5.3 kW/m². The heat distribution on the mould surface is very homogeneous, as shown in Fig. 8. A more accurate surface temperature control will be achieved by placing the controller’s temperature sensor closer to the mould surface.

Fig. 8 EFFICOMP cure tool - heating rates and temperature distribution for a 2.6 mm thick laminate

A scaled version (1.4 m x 1.6 m) of the mould shown in Fig. 2 will be manufactured to validate the concept. The mould-structure will equal the plate level mould with the difference that the TFP heating wire patch and the sandwich core need to be draped on a positive part model. The model will be milled from polyurethane tooling

block boards. For draping the TFP heating wire patch a reverse draping simulation, according to Boehler (2016), will generate the stitching pattern such that a wrinkle free application on the mould is possible. The sandwich core is thermoformed onto the positive model. Application of the reinforcement glass fibre material will be done via standard draping methods. The whole setup will be infiltrated with a vacuum assisted resin infusion process (VARI).

3.4.2. Permanent and semi-permanent release agents

Good release properties are mandatory for a residual free part demoulding, which in return allows several manufacturing cycles without the need for recoating, leading to a reduced mould preparation time. Release properties depend on material properties and their interaction while being exposed to varying environmental conditions (temperature, pressure, humidity, etc.). According to Critchlow et al (2006) a low surface energy, a surface able to form a cohesively weak boundary layer to prevent interdiffusion of the contacting medias, a low molecular mobility and low glass transition temperature of the mould coating (viscoelastic properties) and low surface asperities are responsible for good release properties. Some of those properties are not constant but depend on temperature and pressure conditions. Thus the effectiveness of different release strategies need to be tested using realistic boundary conditions.

Degradation caused by mechanical abrasion over the demoulding processes lead to a short life time of mould surfaces with permanent release properties. A combination of permanent and semi-permanent coatings seems most suited for a compromise between life time and possible non-recoated demoulding cycles.

A testing rig was designed to examine and validate the best suited release strategy for out of autoclave manufacturing cycles with high heating rates. The rig consists of a jig which holds a replaceable cure mould. (Fig. 9 (a)). It is designed to cure the specimen matching the conditions of the intended part cure cycle. For testing, the sample laminate is cured with the rig in cure configuration (Fig. 9 (a)). The vacuum bag and the breather cloth are removed when the demoulding temperature is reached. The peel ply stays on the sample. Then a vacuum gripper, attached to a tensile strength testing machine, is lowered onto the specimen. The applied vacuum holds onto the specimen while the machine pulls it from the mould surface (Fig. 9 (b)). Force and path are measured over time.

Fig. 9 Release strategy testing rig

Three different mould surfaces and two release agent types will be investigated. The permanent mould surfaces will be polished glass fibre reinforced plastic (GFRP) as reference, a gel coat which is applied during mould manufacturing and a PTFE-coating that is applied onto the mould surface. As semi-permanent release agents a water based wax and a solvent based polymer system are tested. Both release agents support spray and wipe application. Release tests will be conducted for those combinations of permanent and semi-permanent release

systems as well as application methods. The goal is to determine the possible amount of demoulding cycles without recoating by measuring the growth of the needed demoulding force over repeated demoulding cycles.

3.4.3. Reusable, heated bagging material

Curing of prepreg material requires control over air transportation in the laminate as well as compaction of the layers. Good air transportation is mandatory for a low part porosity while compaction is responsible for resin flow conditions which influence air transportation and fibre volume fraction of the cured part. Influencing those mechanisms is possible by controlling the vacuum in the laminate, total pressure outside the laminate and resin viscosity via laminate temperature.

For proper vacuum control, the laminate is sealed, using bagging material. Breather-material covering the whole part ensures a constant vacuum distribution within the laminate. Peel plies are used as separating layer to avoid an adhesive connection between breather material and laminate. None of those consumables are drape-able materials. Therefore, their application is a time consuming, manual process.

Fig. 10 Concept heated, reusable bagging material

Reusable bagging materials are investigated to minimize the needed time for the application of the vacuum bag. Furthermore, integration of heating patches into the reusable bagging material to reduce temperature deltas over part thickness and its effects on needed cure time is studied. The investigated concept is shown in Fig. 10.

The membrane consists of silicone reinforced by a base fabric. The base fabric ensures that the membrane represents the part geometry of the cured part. It as well increases the membrane life time by reducing elongation stress of the silicone during the application and removal steps. The silicone allows elastic deformation to enable a homogeneous compaction of the laminate. Two ventilation lines for evacuation are integrated into the mould. The line inside the seal gap is used to pull the membrane into the gap and thereby sealing the laminate from the environment. The line connected to the breather material is used to evacuate the laminate.

Different silicones, base fabrics and heating patches are investigated. Shore A hardness from 10 to 30 for the silicone, base fabrics elongations between 10 and 150 % as well as different heating wire patch patterns and installed electrical power are studied.

Since out of autoclave prepreps are cured with a maximum consolidation pressure of one atmosphere, fibre compaction is critical to ensure low part porosity. Trapped air needs to be removed during the cure cycle rather than its volume shrunk by pressure as done in autoclave processes. Cure trials will be conducted to validate possible laminate quality, especially porosity, as well as cure cycle time, using the different reusable membranes and comparing them to the results of standard bagging material.

4. Conclusion

A new tape placement process and its corresponding previous and flowing process steps were described with the focus on minimizing total process cycle time. A strategy from part – CAD over the manufacturing process to the cured part was presented. The strategy includes software tools for process simulation which consider material behaviour and an automatic transfer from the ply book into robot machine code. Furthermore, concepts for

reducing time consuming sub process step such as mould cleaning, release agent application and vacuum bag application were addressed. Testing rigs were designed to validate those concepts using realistic boundary conditions. Moreover, a heating concept for heating the top and lower laminate and allowing very high heating rates with little temperature distribution deviations was introduced.

Currently the concept, the hardware of the needed testing rigs and the APP process cell exist. For validation of the APP approach a validation element, a scaled version (1.4 m x 1.6 m) of the part shown in Fig. 2, will be manufactured. The manufacturing process will consider results from the trials described in this paper and will use the most suited combination of release system, mould surface, reusable bagging and heating concept.

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